

KLAKLAK-containing agents for attenuation of skin lesions in 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene-induced atopic dermatitis-like inflammation: is that a new approach?

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Abstract

Atopic dermatitis is a chronic inflammatory skin disease with significant health and social importance. Unfortunately, currently there is no well-defined effective treatment. Thus, the search for new therapeutic approaches is currently ongoing. This study presents the clinical impact on skin inflammation induced by 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene in a rat model, after local treatment with the peptide (KLAKLAK)₂-NH₂ (Si1) and a shortened analogue containing non-proteinogenic amino acid β-Ala conjugated with 1,8-naphthalimide (Npht) as second pharmacophore (NphtG-KLβAKLβAK-NH₂ (Si2)). The changes in skin lesions were estimated along with ear thickness determination, and plasma IL4 and IL13 levels evaluation. The results showed attenuation of skin lesions by NphtG-KLβAKLβAK-NH₂ (Si2), accompanied by respective changes in ear thickness, and IL plasma levels. The beneficial effect of the topically applied specifically designed bioconjugate could be attributed to attenuation of skin inflammation due to the pro-apoptotic effect of KLAKLAK moiety on M2 macrophages engaged in the pathological process.

Keywords

atopic dermatitis, KLAKLAK, 1,8-naphthalimide, M2 macrophages, rat model

Introduction

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic skin disease that not only causes subjective discomfort in patients but also provokes serious social disability. Considering that this skin

condition affects up to 1/5th of the population in developed countries (Weidinger and Novak 2016), it is not surprising that AD is one of the most common and intensively studied chronic inflammatory skin diseases. Both the predisposing factors and the pathogenesis, as well as

possible new approaches for the prevention and treatment of the condition, are currently the subject of in-depth studies by many scientific groups (Puar et al. 2021).

The exact pathogenesis of AD is not yet fully revealed, but the specific interaction between a certain genetic predisposition and environmental factors has been conclusively proven (Furue et al. 2019). The genetic predisposition itself may concern features of the skin barrier (Cabanillas et al. 2017; Furue et al. 2017) and the individual's immune response (Werfel et al. 2016; Malik et al. 2017). In both cases, the necessary conditions are created for increased susceptibility of the skin to chronic inflammation (Guttman-Yassky et al. 2017).

Macrophages are important immune cells. They represent antigen-presenting cells involved in inflammation and wound-healing processes. They produce many cytokines and chemokines that stimulate new capillary growth, collagen synthesis, and fibrosis (Mirza et al. 2009). Macrophages are a kind of bridge between innate and adaptive immunity. They interact with other antigen-presenting cells—the dendritic cells—and with other phagocytic cells—the neutrophils—as well as with basophils, T-cells, and even the complement system (Saahene et al. 2022). Their activation is carried out by two possible mechanisms: the so-called classical one and the alternative one. Depending on the type of activation, both mechanisms differ between classically activated macrophages (also named M1) and alternatively activated macrophages (named M2, respectively) (Kasraie and Werfel 2013). On the other hand, monocytes are precursors of macrophages. They invade the dermis and differentiate into macrophages, which further dominate the dermal mononuclear cell infiltrate and can also act as antigen-presenting cells (Vestergaard et al. 2004). Macrophages called „tumor-associated“ have been found in the tumor matrix. They possess the phenotypic characteristics of M2 macrophages. Among their functions, a direct increase of epithelial–mesenchymal transition, extracellular matrix remodeling, and angiogenesis is observed, determining their tumorigenic

effect and the increased ability of the primary tumor to metastasize (Kitamura et al. 2015; Chen et al. 2017).

The present article is based on data revealed through several studies:

- The disclosure of M2 macrophages in relation to acute and chronic skin inflammation (Kiekens et al. 2001).
- The possibility of M2 cells being specifically targeted (albeit currently only in cancer patients) and thus locally destroyed or inhibited (Lee et al. 2019).

The literature review showed that tumor-associated macrophages expressing M2-like phenotypes, and thus contributing to tumorigenicity and metastasis, were targeted with the pro-apoptotic peptide d (KLAKLAK)₂ with high anti-metastatic potential (Lee et al. 2022). In our previous study, it was revealed that the peptide (KLAKLAK)₂-NH₂ (Si1) and the bioconjugate between 1,8-naphthalimide and a KLAKLAK-NH₂ analogue specifically designed to contain the unnatural amino acid β-Ala (NphtG-KLβAKLβAK-NH₂ (Si2)) showed good antitumor and antibacterial activity (Jaber et al. 2021). In addition, Mitamura et al. described that AD is characterized by M2 macrophage-mediated inflammation as a result of high levels of IL-4, IL-5, IL-13, and IL-31 secreted by Th2 lymphocytes (Mitamura et al. 2023). Taking this discovery into account, herein the ability of Si1 and Si2 to influence AD inflammation in rats induced by treatment with 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene is investigated. Moreover, the moiety 1,8-naphthalimide possesses many additional properties such as antitumor (Marinov et al. 2019; Lee et al. 2024), antioxidant (Kamal et al. 2013), and anti-inflammatory activity (Shao et al. 2013) (Oettgen and Geha 1999; De Souza et al. 2002). Thus, the hypothesis for a synergic effect between both parts of the molecule exists.

Hence, the working scientific hypothesis was that reducing the levels of M2 macrophages would have a positive effect in a model of AD (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. A. Release of IL-4, IL-5, IL-13, and IL-31 from Th2 lymphocytes, which drives the differentiation of macrophages into M2 and increases inflammation; B. Si1 and Si2 induce apoptosis of M2 and reduce the pro-inflammatory changes.

Results and discussion

Clinical evaluation of DNCB-induced AD-like skin lesions

The induction of AD according to the described methodology led to the development of characteristic manifestations: redness, swelling, and thickening of the skin, excoriations, and ulcerations (Fig. 2C, D). Total scores are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Clinical evaluation of 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene-induced AD in different experimental groups: 1. Negative control group—abdominally treated; 2. Negative control group—dorsally treated; 3. Positive control (AD) group—abdominally treated; 4. Positive control (AD) group—dorsally treated; 5. Abdominally Si1-treated group; 6. Dorsally Si1-treated group; 7. Abdominally Si2-treated group; 8. Dorsally Si2-treated group.

Group	Erythema	Edema/infiltration	Scratching marks	Total
1	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0
3	3	3	2	8
4	2	3	3	8
5	2	0	1	3
6	1	1	2	4
7	2	0	0	2
8	1	0	2	3

Si1 and Si2 reduced all three reported indicators, with Si2 (Fig. 2G, H, Table 1, groups 7 and 8) showing a slightly lower total score than Si1 (Fig. 2E, F, Table 1, groups 5 and 6). It is also noticeable that the abdominal surfaces (Fig. 2E, G, Table 1, groups 5 and 7) are more highly affected compared to the dorsal ones (Fig. 2F, H, Table 1, groups 6 and 8).

Local pretreatment of the sensitized skin areas with the newly synthesized substances Si1 and Si2 before the provocations showed a decrease in the total score of the appearance of skin lesions. The beneficial effect of the newly synthesized peptides on AD-like inflammatory lesions could be attributed to the pro-apoptotic effect of the KLAKLAK-NH₂ moiety as well as the second pharmacophore, 1,8-naphthalimide, introduced in the tested bioconjugate and acting on M2 macrophages. Such an effect may result in a decrease in their number at the site of the lesion, and thus in the levels of the pro-inflammatory mediators released by them in the pretreated areas. Reducing the number of M2 macrophages locally would improve the skin barrier function. It could be expected that the improved resistance of the skin barrier is associated with a reduced level of local as well as systemic inflammation—the latter evidenced by lowered IL-4 and IL-13 plasma levels (see below).

Serum IL-4 and IL-13 levels evaluation

IL-4 and IL-13 levels were determined given their proven involvement in M2 macrophage differentiation [16]. Furthermore, they are also indicators of the systemic pro-inflammatory potential of the induced AD-like model in rats.

The levels of both interleukins increased in animals with induced AD compared to the controls. The increase was more significant on day 30 of the study (Fig. 3A, B). Pretreatment with the newly synthesized substances Si1 and Si2 prevented the increase in both interleukins on day 20 of the study. On day 30, increased levels of IL-4 were reported after Si2 pretreatment, while IL-13 levels increased after pretreatment with Si1 (Fig. 3A, B).

Figure 2. Clinical manifestations in different experimental groups. Documentation of skin lesions was performed on day 30, immediately before euthanizing the animals. Shown are the abdominal (A) and dorsal (B) surfaces of the negative control group; the abdominal (C) and dorsal (D) surfaces of the positive control group (AD group); the abdominal (E) and dorsal (F) surfaces of the Si1-treated group; and the abdominal (G) and dorsal (H) surfaces of the Si2-treated group.

Figure 3. A. IL-4 levels; B. IL-13 levels. Concentrations were measured at 450 nm absorption. Groups with induced AD (AD) were compared with controls: +++ $p < 0.001$; groups with pretreatment (Si1 and Si2) were compared with AD: *** $p < 0.001$.

These two interleukins were not chosen randomly. It is well known that IL-4 and IL-13 are more specifically associated with the pathogenesis of AD. They induce the transcription of germ-line immune cells that produce the IgE isotype while at the same time inhibiting the production of Th1 cytokines (Oettgen and Geha 1999). At the same time, they stimulate the activation of M2 macrophages (Kasraie and Werfel 2013). Our results show that on day 20 of the study, the levels of both interleukins were reduced. This gives reason to suspect both a local effect and a certain systemic effect on inflammation. However, neither of the two newly synthesized substances prevented the increase in both interleukins on day 30. This means that systemic inflammation is present, although probably to a lesser extent.

The data obtained from the clinical response of skin lesions and determination of IL-4 and IL-13 levels provide grounds to assume that Si1 and Si2 affect local inflammation. This could be due to their effect on M2

macrophages or other cells (e.g., CD8+). The α -helical amphipathic peptide (KLAKLAK)₂-NH₂ has antibacterial properties due to its ability to disrupt the bacterial cell membrane simultaneously with lower toxicity to eukaryotic cells (Javadrou et al. 1996). In addition, (KLAKLAK)₂-NH₂ disrupts mitochondrial membranes and causes the release of cytochrome C, which triggers apoptosis (Ellerby et al. 1999). The pro-apoptotic effect on M2 macrophages probably also reduces the levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Macrophage activation plays a significant role in inflammation as it aims to destroy invading pathogens. Excessive activation, however, changes the balance between beneficial effects and damage, with a predominance of the latter (Vallerdor et al. 2010). The potential effect of the KLAKLAK moiety on macrophages has been demonstrated (Czapla et al. 2024). However, given the reported better clinical outcome after Si2, the synergistic effect of the two pharmacophores should be highlighted.

Pinnas' thickness evaluation

Pinnas' thickness measurements in animals from the negative control group showed no differences between the left and right ones. In the positive control group, thickening of both the left and right (auto-control) pinnas was found compared to the negative control group. The reported thickening was 2-fold in the left and 1.4 times in the right pinnas. Topical pretreatment with both Si1 and Si2 did not show statistically relevant differences from the positive controls for the left pinnas. The right ones instead were estimated to be approximately 46% thinner than the positive control group's left pinnas and approximately 26% thinner than the positive control group's right pinnas. They were still approximately 10% thicker than the negative control group's right pinnas. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Thickness of left (experimental) and right (auto-control) auricles in the experimental groups. AD, positive control group with atopic dermatitis; C, negative control group; Si1 and Si2, groups of animals treated with Si1 and Si2, respectively.

Group	Left ear (mm)	Right ear (mm)
C	0.52	0.51
AD	1.05	0.75
Si1	1.04	0.57
Si2	1.04	0.55

The data from the study of ear thickness support the local effect of Si1 and Si2. The ears were not pretreated before the provocation. Therefore, the thickening of the left auricles is due to the direct local effect of DNCB. The relatively weaker but significant thickening of the right auricles is an indirect effect of the systemic manifestation following the local inflammatory process in the skin. The weaker thickening of the auto-control ears is probably due to the weaker systemic effect. The latter is a consequence of the attenuating local effect of Si1 and Si2 on the skin lesions.

In some cases, AD is difficult to treat, which justifies the search for new therapeutic approaches. Local methods of treatment are preferred over systemic drug administration because they are theoretically associated with fewer side effects. The possibility of locally limiting the pro-inflammatory effect of cells involved in the pathogenesis of AD lesions by reducing their number (and thus pro-inflammatory activity) is attractive and would find its place in future therapeutic protocols.

It is possible that the beneficial effect is due to other factors. It is known that endothelial cells express adhesion molecules through which they regulate the entry of monocytes into a certain vascular or tissue area. It is possible that the KLAKLAK moiety alters the expression of specific adhesion molecules, which sets a direction for future studies.

Conclusion

The study shows that there are no limits to the therapeutic potential of drug molecules. A molecule, in this case

(KLAKLAK)₂-NH₂, which was initially associated with anti-tumor therapy, could find application in the treatment of another type of pathology very different from the neoplastic one. This is due to its relationship with inflammatory processes. Inflammation, as a typical pathophysiological process, is at the heart of human pathology and has a role in the pathogenesis of both atopic dermatitis and neoplasia. It is likely that the beneficial effect of topical pretreatment with (KLAKLAK)₂-NH₂-containing conjugates on AD-like inflammatory lesions reduces the local inflammatory process and attenuates the subsequent systemic manifestations after the provocation.

The specific mechanisms of the (KLAKLAK)₂-NH₂ positive effect would be an interesting and promising subject for future research.

Experimental

Experimental animals

The experiments were carried out on male Wistar rats weighing 420 ± 20 g at the beginning of the experiments. Animals were obtained from the Medical University of Sofia Vivarium (Registration № 1431-0001). Rats were subdivided into 8 groups (*n* = 6–8 per group), housed under controlled temperature (22 °C ± 2 °C) and a 12 h light/dark cycle (light between 08:00 and 20:00), and treated as described in detail below. All experimental protocol procedures were conducted in accordance with the relevant European Community requirements and approved by the BFSa (Permission protocol № 353/30.05.2023).

Experimental groups

All experiments with animals were conducted between 9:00 and 12:00 a.m., according to the "Principles of Laboratory Animal Care" (NIH Publication No. 85-23, revised 1985) and with permit № 353/14.06.2023 from the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency.

1. Negative control-A (control group-A, NC-A group) (*n* = 8)—animals were treated with 0.9% NaCl on shaved abdominal skin areas;
2. Negative control-D (control group-D, NC-D group) (*n* = 8)—animals were treated with 0.9% NaCl on shaved dorsal skin areas;
3. Positive control-A (atopic dermatitis, AD-A group) (*n* = 6)—animals in which 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene AD was induced on abdominal surfaces;
4. Positive control-D (atopic dermatitis, AD-D group) (*n* = 6)—animals in which 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene AD was induced on dorsal surfaces;
5. Si1-A group (*n* = 6)—animals in which abdominal surfaces were sensitized as described in Fig. 2; 10 min before challenges with 200 µL of 1% DNCB solution on days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29, the sensitized abdominal surfaces were treated locally with 200 µL of 2.81 mM Si1 solution. The left ear of each

- animal was treated with 20 μ L of 1% DNCB solution during challenges on days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29;
6. Si1-D group ($n = 6$)—animals in which dorsal surfaces were sensitized as described in Fig. 2; 10 min before challenges with 200 μ L of 1% DNCB solution on days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29, the sensitized dorsal surfaces were treated locally with 200 μ L of 2.81 mM Si1 solution. The left ear of each animal was treated with 20 μ L of 1% DNCB solution during challenges on days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29;
 7. Si2-A group ($n = 6$)—animals in which abdominal surfaces were sensitized as described in Fig. 2; 10 min before challenges with 200 μ L of 1% DNCB solution on days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29, the sensitized abdominal surfaces were treated locally with 200 μ L of 2.81 mM Si2 solution. The left ear of each animal was treated with 20 μ L of 1% DNCB solution during challenges on days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29;
 8. Si2-D group ($n = 6$)—animals in which dorsal surfaces were sensitized as described in Fig. 2; 10 min before challenges with 200 μ L of 1% DNCB solution on days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29, the sensitized dorsal surfaces were treated locally with 200 μ L of 2.81 mM Si2 solution. The left ear of each animal was treated with 20 μ L of 1% DNCB solution during challenges on days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29.

The procedures applied to each one of the groups are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Experimental group descriptions.

N ^o	Group	Abbreviation	Treatment
1	Negative control-A	C-A	Shaved abdominal surfaces of animals in this group were treated only with saline
2	Negative control-D	C-D	Shaved dorsal surfaces of animals in this group were treated only with saline
3	Positive control-A	AD-A	1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene AD was induced on abdominal surfaces
4	Positive control-D	AD-D	1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene AD was induced on dorsal surfaces
5	Experimental 1	Si1-A	Before provocation, animals' abdominal surfaces were locally pretreated with the Si1 substance
6	Experimental 2	Si1-D	Before provocation, animals' dorsal surfaces were locally pretreated with the Si1 substance
7	Experimental 3	Si2-A	Before provocation, animals' abdominal surfaces were locally pretreated with the Si2 substance
8	Experimental 4	Si2-D	Before provocation, animals' dorsal surfaces were locally pretreated with the Si2 substance

Table 4. Sensitization (days 1, 2, and 3), pretreatments (days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29), and provocation (days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29) of animals in each one of the groups. DNCB, 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene.

Group	Sensibilization		Pretreatment		Provocation		
	A	D	A	D	A	D	LE
1	0.9% NaCl	-	-	-	0.9% NaCl	-	-
2	-	0.9% NaCl	-	-	-	0.9% NaCl	-
3	200 μ L of 0.7% DNCB*	-	-	-	200 μ L of 1% DNCB	-	20 μ L of 1% DNCB
4	-	200 μ L of 0.7% DNCB	-	-	-	200 μ L of 1% DNCB	20 μ L of 1% DNCB
5	200 μ L of 0.7% DNCB	-	200 μ L of Si1	-	200 μ L of 1% DNCB	-	20 μ L of 1% DNCB
6	-	200 μ L of 0.7% DNCB	-	200 μ L of Si1	-	200 μ L of 1% DNCB	20 μ L of 1% DNCB
7	200 μ L of 0.7% DNCB	-	200 μ L of Si2	-	200 μ L of 1% DNCB	-	20 μ L of 1% DNCB
8	-	200 μ L of 0.7% DNCB	-	200 μ L of Si2	-	200 μ L of 1% DNCB	20 μ L of 1% DNCB

A more detailed description of the treatments is presented in Table 4.

Atopic dermatitis study

AD-like inflammation was induced by treating abdominal or dorsal surfaces (Fig. 4B, C) with 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (DNCB) according to a protocol borrowed from Chan et al. (2013), schematically represented in Fig. 4A. A total of 200 μ L of 0.7% DNCB (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) in acetone/olive oil (3:1) was applied to the shaved area on days 1–3. On days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29, rats were challenged with 200 μ L of 1% DNCB applied to the shaved dorsal (Fig. 4B) or abdominal (Fig. 4C) skin area and 20 μ L of 1% DNCB to the left ear (Fig. 4D).

Evaluation of interleukin levels

Blood samples for interleukin level evaluation were obtained on day 20 of the experiment (after the third provocation treatment) and on day 30, immediately prior to the animals' sacrifice.

IL-4 and IL-13 are closely related Th2-mediated immune response cytokines that share receptor components and signaling pathways. Together, they suppress the classical Th1-mediated pro-inflammatory cascade while promoting a Th2-mediated immune response, including IgE production, alternative activation of macrophages with polarization toward the M2 phenotype,

Figure 4. A. Schematic representation of the experimental setup for inducing atopic dermatitis-like lesions. Animals (experimental AD group) were sensitized three times with 200 µL of 0.7% DNCB solution on days 1, 2, and 3. Treatment was applied to the abdominal or dorsal surface, shaved the day before the start of the experiment. The provocation was carried out six times at 3-day intervals, starting from day 14 and counting from the first day of sensitization (days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29), and included 1) treatment of presensitized abdominal or dorsal surfaces with 200 µL of 1% DNCB solution and 2) treatment of the unsensitized left ear of the animals with 20 µL of 1% DNCB solution. The sensitized skin areas are shown in shaded ovals (B) dorsally and (C) abdominally. Densitometric determination of the thickness of the external ear was made in the shaded section (D).

and tissue remodeling. IL-4 is dominant in T-cell differentiation and B-cell class switching associated with the Th2-mediated immune response. IL-13 exerts stronger effects on epithelial cells, stimulating mucus production and fibrotic processes. Functionally, both cytokines are anti-inflammatory in immune regulatory mechanisms but become pathogenic when overexpressed in chronic inflammatory conditions (Saahene et al. 2022).

Quantification of human IL-4 and IL-13 by ELISA

Human IL-4 and IL-13 levels were quantified using the LEGEND MAX™ Human IL-4 and IL-13 ELISA kits (BioLegend), respectively. Both are sandwich ELISAs utilizing 96-well plates precoated with monoclonal anti-human antibodies specific for IL-4 and IL-13. Detection was performed using biotinylated secondary antibodies followed by avidin-HRP.

Both assays were performed strictly according to the manufacturer's instructions: BioLegend LEGEND MAX™ Human IL-4 ELISA Kit Cat. No. 430307 and BioLegend LEGEND MAX™ Human IL-13 ELISA Kit Cat. No. 435207.

Assay procedure

Pre-prepared plasma samples were analyzed. All reagents were equilibrated to room temperature prior to use. For each assay, a standard curve ranging from 3.2 to 200 pg/mL was prepared via serial dilution. For plasma

samples, 50 µL of Assay Buffer A was added per well, followed by 50 µL of sample. For standards, 50 µL of Matrix C and 50 µL of standard dilution were added. Plates were incubated for 2 h at room temperature with shaking (200 rpm), washed, and incubated with 100 µL of the respective detection antibody for 1 h. After washing, 100 µL of avidin-HRP was added and incubated for 30 min. Following final washes, 100 µL of substrate solution F was added and incubated in the dark for 15 min. The reaction was stopped with 100 µL of Stop Solution, and absorbance was measured at 450 nm within 30 min.

Chemicals

1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (DNCB) was purchased from Sigma–Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) and administered in acetone/olive oil (3:1) vehicle.

(KLAKLAK)₂-NH₂ (Si1) and 1,8-NphtG-KLβAK-LβAK-NH₂ (Si2) were previously synthesized and described by Jaber et al. (2021). Briefly, both molecules, Si1 and Si2, were synthesized on Fmoc-Rink amide MBHA resin using N,N,N',N'-tetramethyl-O-(1H-benzotriazol-1-yl) uronium hexafluorophosphate, N,N'-diisopropylcarbodiimide, or benzotriazol-1-yl-xytripyrrolidinophosphonium hexafluorophosphate as coupling reagents for different steps of synthesis (Iris Biotech, Wunsiedel, Germany). The final targeted molecules were deprotected and released from the resin

Table 5. Criteria for evaluation of skin lesions in experimental animals.

Sign	None	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Erythema	No visible redness	Slightly visible redness	Clearly visible redness	Dark red skin
Edema	No visible swelling	Slight elevation	Clearly perceptible elevation	Prominent elevation
Dryness	No visible thickening or skin lines	Barely visible skin lines	Clearly exaggerated skin lines	Skin thickening with exaggerated skin lines
Excoriation	No visible scratching marks	Superficial excoriation	Deeper excoriation(s)	Several deep excoriations

by treatment with a mixture of 95% trifluoroacetic acid, 2.5% triisopropylsilane, and 2.5% distilled water for 4 h. The raw TFA extract of the peptide was crystallized by adding cold diethyl ether to the obtained oil. All characteristics of both molecules have already been published by Jaber et al. (2021). The chromatographic purity of the targeted peptides is 100%.

Both newly synthesized substances were administered in the same acetone/olive oil (3:1) vehicle as described above for DNCB.

Evaluation of dermatitis severity

The severity of dermatitis was measured at the end of the experiment (day 30). Symptoms of erythema, edema, dryness or scarring, and excoriation or erosion were scored on a scale of zero (none), one (mild), two (moderate), or three (severe). The exact criteria are shown in Table 5, adapted for rats from those previously described for humans by Leung et al. (1990). Total dermatitis scores (ranging from 0 to 9) of each one of the experimental groups were calculated as the sum of the individual scores determined by two investigators (blind to the experiments); inter-observer error did not vary by more than 3%.

The thickness of the left and right (auto-control) ears of the animals in each group was determined using an electronic digital caliper in the middle of the external ear of the animal (indicated in Fig. 4D).

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: 353/14.06.2023.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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